

Electronic supplementary material text, figures and tables (S1)

to

Increase in marine provinciality over the last 250 million years governed more by climate change than plate tectonics

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Supplementary Methods

Measuring provinciality

The membership distribution of geographic cells (probability mass function of province sizes) is analogous to abundance distributions of ecological samples. Cells take the place of specimens and provinces (rather than species) become categories. Unlike abundance distributions, the richness and evenness attributes of the distribution constrain each other in the case of biogeographic membership. Thus, an evenness metric of the membership distribution indirectly incorporates the number of provinces.

The number of sampled provinces is a metric that is extremely sensitive to heterogeneous sampling (figure S1.1). Provinces are spatially aggregated groups of cells and spatial clustering of samples lead to highly heterogeneous sampling of the cell-membership distribution. Our provinciality metric (PIE) makes no assumptions about this distribution.

PIE is considered insensitive to sample size [47], which in this case is the number of sampled geographic cells in a time slice. It also has the desirable attribute of being constrained between 0 (only one province) and 1 (each cell represents a different province). PIE index of provinciality is insensitive to the geographic resolution of analyses (figure S1.2) and decreases the effects of ‘noise-modules’ (provinces), which are partitions that arise due to extremely low locality-level sampling [24]. However, even PIE can be biased by inhomogeneous sampling that characterizes the fossil record [6], which indicated the spatially complete, simulation-based approach to reconstruct the evolution of provinciality.

Simulation details

SST and habitat reconstructions

The simulations relied on spatially accurate reconstructions of habitat area and mean annual SSTs that represent average conditions at a locality in a stage. The distribution of shallow marine habitats was based on a series of 81 maps that incorporates marine and terrestrial fossil occurrences from the PaleoDB to define maximum transgressive surfaces on the series of PaleoDEMs (PaleoMAP Paleocoastlines [28]).

The palaeoclimate simulations have been compared to available benthic and surface proxy climate records and the model performs well with respect to sea surface temperature, except that temperature changes in high latitudes (polewards of $\sim 60^\circ$) are underestimated. This is a common problem of most climate models. Climate models were generated based on the PaleoDEMs. As the coastlines were corrected to represent maximum transgressive states, some of the shelf areas had no reconstructed SST values in the climate output. Although the changing coastlines will influence the output of the climate models to a minor extent, re-running them for the whole Phanerozoic is computationally expensive. Therefore, we decided to interpolate these missing values and discard the slight, potential changes that might result due to the changing topography. First, the original 3×2 -degree model output was rescaled to a 1×1 -degree grid. Interpolations were executed using thin plate spline regression as implemented in the R package ‘fields’ (v10.3) [48]. The interpolated values were then masked with updated coastlines.

Barriers between climatic belts

The simulation framework was based on our previous study on modern benthic biogeography [24] that aimed to find an optimal partitioning method that would lead to comparable biogeographic structures in recent and fossil settings. The results included a biogeographic partitioning (figure S1.3a), where each province (there: ‘bioregion’) could be assigned unequivocally to a latitudinal zone.

The simulation process starts with reconstructing where present-day climatic zones might have been, given past SST reconstructions. As the range of SSTs covered by present-day provinces overlap, we decided to describe the relationship between SST values and the climatic zone of a province using a machine learning approach that can handle complicated, non-linear associations.

Each geographic cell of the original partitioning [24] was assigned a categorical value of either 1, 2 or 3, depending on whether it belonged to a province in the polar, temperate, or tropical zone, respectively. Then we trained a neural network using the ‘neuralnet’ (v1.44.2) R package [49] to predict the latitudinal zone identifiers from the cells’ SST values. The network consisted of two

hidden layers (4 and 3 neurons), the maximum number of steps were increased to 10^6 from the default value. We used the forward propagation implemented in the `predict.nn()` function for all 81 time slices.

The result of this process is the reconstructed positions of polar, temperate and tropical zones in past reconstructions using their present-day temperature values as their defining criterion. The simulations infer biogeographic barriers between provinces at the boundaries of these zones (but see ‘Small regions’ below, where this might not be the case).

Barriers within climatic zones: distance matrix and minimum spanning tree construction

In every time slice, the coastline shapefiles were used to look up which cells in the simulation grid contained seawater. We calculated the minimum water distances between all water-cells expressed as number of cells using the ‘igraph’ R package (v1.2.6) [50]. The distance matrix was subset to only contain shelf cells. We simulated how each zone can be dissected to provinces by translating oceanic and landmass barriers to a minimum distance threshold between two provinces. In our simulation procedure, if the minimum water distance between two patches exceeds this threshold (d_t), the two patches are assigned to two different biogeographic provinces.

To implement this process, in each latitudinal zone we selected that part of the distance matrix that contained shelf cells and constructed a minimum spanning tree (MST) from it using the R package ‘vegan’ (v2.5-7) [51]. The longest branches of this MST represent shortest routes between patches of shelf area. We then cut all branches of the MST that were longer than the predefined parameter d_t and tabulated the connected components of the graph representation of the MST. The process was then iterated for every latitudinal zone.

Small regions

Small provinces frequently emerge due to the complex interference of coastlines and climatic zone boundaries. Such small provinces are unlikely to be detected by data analysis methods because of the coarser geographic resolution or be declared separate entities by experts (single islands do not become provinces). This noise was dampened by the joining of small provinces with the closest neighbouring provinces.

Free parameters

The simulation mechanism incorporates two parameters that can be arbitrarily chosen: the dispersion threshold or threshold length of minimum-spanning tree for breaking the latitudinal zone to geographic regions (d_t), and the minimum region size (s_{min}).

Both d_t and s_{min} values were selected so the simulation can replicate patterns of recent

biogeography using the present-day continent configuration and SST distribution. d_t was chosen as the maximum value that separated the relatively close temperate Australian and New-Zealandian provinces, which represented different biogeographic entities for millions of years. The minimum size of the provinces (s_{min}) was set to 45 cells, so smaller parts of shelf patches that cross a latitudinal zone boundary indicated by the simulations (e.g. New Zealand shelf, Kerguelen plateau, Northwestern Atlantic) would not represent different provinces, as they are not indicated so by the present-day biogeography.

Although these parameters produced remarkably good results in replicating present-day biogeography (figure S1.3), they are nevertheless somewhat arbitrary and their applicability in deep time is based on uniformitarian assumptions. Therefore, we conducted sensitivity tests varying d_t and s_{min} separately, while the other was held constant. The Phanerozoic-scale simulations were redone with setting the d_t parameter to 0.01, 0.02, 0.08, 0.12, 0.16 and 0.2, and s_{min} took the values 0, 5, 10, 30, 50 and 100 cells.

Partial simulations

One of the greatest advantages of simulation modelling is that it can be used to experiment with how independent processes influence a joint output given the pre-defined mechanics. Using the same simulation settings as before, we addressed two main questions with partial simulations. (1) what would provinciality be like if climate had not changed over time? (2) What would provinciality be like if the continents had not moved? Additionally, we asked if one of these ‘parameters’ did not change, what is the contribution of the other to the overall simulation output? These hypothetical scenarios were implemented using the same processes as the main approach above (which is labelled ‘dynamic’ in this document), only the forcing SST data and palaeogeographic reconstructions were modified and/or recombined.

For the scenario with stable climate and changing continental configuration (*changingCC*), we generated simplified latitudinal SST gradients based on the present-day SST distribution. The present-day SST was modelled as a function of absolute latitude with regression trees implemented in the R package ‘randomForest’ (4.6-14) [52], which predicted an expected SST value for every latitude. Values from this gradient replaced the original SST values in the deep-time reconstructions and were used with the original palaeogeographic data.

For the scenario with stable continent configuration and changing climate (*changingT*), we repeated the modelling in the paragraph above for every time slice with reconstructed SSTs to generate an average latitudinal SST gradient for every time slice. These gradients were then used with the present-day continental configuration to represent past time slices. These SST models do not include

spatial details that characterize climate model outputs, such as gyres and hemispheric asymmetry. Although it is possible to generate these outputs using actual climate simulations, these would be extremely resource demanding.

Both simulations were also masked with the fossil record, similarly to the ‘dynamic’ output, to assess how sampling might affect the apparent forcing of provinciality.

Simulation post-processing

Biogeographic partitionings that we derived from fossil data analysis and simulations needed to be structured in time using different timescales (stage-level, 95-bin vs. 81-bin, respectively, supplementary table S1.1). We assigned a simulation output to every stage-level bin based on its age, whichever was the closest to it in time.

Biogeographic analysis of fossil occurrence data

Preparation of fossil occurrence data

Accepted species names were used when provided, otherwise entered species names were used. Occurrences that were not identified to the species level were omitted, species with uncertain identifications were kept. The culling of non-species level data affected the number of collections only to a minor extent (dropping from 82 656 to 75 440, 91% retained). The palaeocoordinates of collections were calculated using the Gplates 2.2.0 [53] software with the ‘rgplates’ R package (v0.1.0) [54] and the PALEOMAP global plate tectonic model [55]. After filtering, 423 981 occurrences remained in the dataset for analysis. Fossil collections were binned into similar, but somewhat coarser grid cells [29] than used for the simulations (mean cell area of approximately one million km²).

Biogeographic partitioning

First, a species-spatiotemporal cell bipartite network was constructed, which was then transformed (projected) to a unipartite network where only the spatiotemporal cells were represented (figure 1b). Cells with fewer than five occurrences were discarded (~25%) because they were shown to dramatically increase the number of ‘noise modules’ (bioregions) [24] (Figure S1.8a therein). After correcting the network edge-weights for sampling intensity [19], the ‘infomap’ community detection algorithm [56] was applied to the network that contains only spatiotemporal cells as vertices. The ‘igraph’ [50] implementation was used to produce the main results of the study, with the number of trials set to the default value of 10. Setting this parameter to higher values (e.g. 100) yielded identical results.

The results were contrasted with those derived from using the Infomap console application (www.mapequation.org, v1.3 and v0.21.0) as the latter exposes more parameters of the method to the user. We experimented with values of 0, 0.15 (default), 0.3 and 0.45 for both the teleportation probability and the self-link teleportation probability (only in Infomap v0.21.0). The application was configured to produce the ‘two-level’ optimization, which is comparable to the ‘igraph’ implementation. The number of attempted clustering trials was set to 10.

To demonstrate the effects that overall network might have on the biogeographies, we repeated the partitioning algorithm on time bin-specific subsets of the original data (figure S1.4), so partitioning in any time bin does not depend on the information of other time-bins. The code of the partitioning procedure was implemented using ‘igraph’ [50] and had been packaged in the R extension ‘obigeo’ (v0.2.2) [57].

Analysis of fossil data-based biogeographic partitionings

Durations of all observed modules (provinces) were tabulated. Mean province duration was calculated for every stage based on the provinces that range through that stage. As sampling heterogeneity disproportionately influences the number of single-interval entities [58], provinces spanning only a single-interval were discarded. Some provinces contain spatiotemporal cells that are scattered away in time from the coherent body of the province, which disproportionately extend the temporal range of some provinces (figure S1.8a). For the calculation of province durations, we omitted those range endpoints where these two criteria were met: 1) the start or end of the province’s range was represented by a single cell in a stage; and 2) where these single cells were separated from the rest of province’s cells by at least one stage in which no cell belonged to the province. The procedures were repeated without extant taxa as these are expected to have shorter than average durations.

Geographic resolution and resampling

The fossil data analysis and the biogeographic simulations relied on different geographic grids as the low density of fossil occurrences limits the spatial resolution of environmental reconstructions. To contrast results and simulate how patterns of sampling influences the simulation output, the simulated biogeographic partitionings had to be resampled to match the grid of fossil data analysis. The positions of the cell centroids of the fine-resolution (simulation) grid were looked up in the coarse resolution (analysis) grid. Then cells of the coarse resolution grid were assigned a province membership depending on which province most of the fine resolution cells in it belonged to. In case multiple provinces were represented with the same maximum number, one was assigned randomly.

Fossil data analysis

Mean global water temperature and shelf area were originally available for the 81-bin time scale, whereas fossil provinciality calculations were based on the 95-bin time scale (table S3). The coarser one was used to model provinciality calculated from fossil data. Finer resolution series (provinciality series, continent fragmentation index [4]) were matched to the same dates using splines implemented in the `asplines()` function in the ‘akima’ R package (v0.6-2.1) [59].

We then modelled provinciality using a simple linear model:

$$provinciality \sim shelfarea * cont.frag. * sst$$

Model selection [60] indicated that most interaction terms did not substantially contribute to the model. After removing these variables from the model, we tested for potential autocorrelations of residuals in this simplified model. As significant autocorrelations were present, the suggested predictor variables ($shelfarea + cont.frag + sst + sst:cont.frag$) were then assessed using a GLS model. The `auto.arima()` function from the ‘forecast’ package (v8.14) [61] was used to determine which autoregressive (AR) or moving average (MA) components best characterize the residuals of the linear model. The suggested process was then used as correlation structure in GLS.

Diversity (figure S1.5) was regressed in a similar fashion, only it was assessed with 1) provinciality being a single predictor variable, and 2) with provinciality added to those listed in the paragraph above.

Simulation data

Provinciality values in the ‘dynamic’ simulation output were modelled with provincialities of the two partial simulation sets. The temporal resolution for the spatially complete set (figures 3 and S1.6a) matched that of the provinciality-modelling with fossil data (81-bin), as in every simulated set one simulated provinciality value was produced for every time bin. As the sampling-mask was based on fossil biogeographies that used the 95-bin timescale, modelling with the masked simulation series (figures 3 and S1.6b) was also based on this timescale.

The modelling process was same as for provincialities based on fossil data. Only the original formula was replaced with the

$$dynamic \sim changingT + changingCC$$

formula.

Correlations and differences

Simple correlations were assessed using Spearman's rank order coefficient. We calculated the 95% confidence interval of these statistics using bootstrap simulations. Median differences were assessed using a similar approach, by calculating the distribution of differences in medians in the bootstrap replicates of the samples. Both approaches used 10 000 iterations.

Code and dependencies

All analyses were run in the R programming environment [62]. PaleoDB, Paleocoastlines and SST data were imported using the 'chronosphere' framework [63]. Besides those already mentioned, functions were called from the namespaces of the following additional R extension packages: 'entropy' v1.2.1 [64]; 'geosphere' v1.5-10 [65]; 'nlme' v3.1-152 [66]; 'raster' v3.4-5 [67]; 'rgdal' v1.5-23 [68], 'rgeos' v0.5-5 [69], 'sp' v1.4-5 [70], restools v0.11 [71].

Supplementary Results and Discussion

Match of simulation output and present-day biogeography

The dynamic simulation output manages to reproduce almost all provinces indicated by present-day species distributions with remarkable accuracy (figure S1.3). Some slight differences do occur, however. Simulations indicate the presence of a Southwest temperate Atlantic province, which does not appear in the empirical partitioning results. Several reasons may explain this phenomenon. Covert provinces along the temperate coasts of the Americas might not show up in real partitionings due to the small area of shelf habitat. The coarseness of geographic resolution might blend multiple provinces together. Finally, the much lower sampling intensity in the Antarctic province might distort the observed patterns.

The two tropical provinces separated by the Middle American landmass are joint in the simulation output. The simulation relies on the graph mesh outlines by the connectivity patterns of the grid cells, and neighbouring cells are assumed to be connected automatically. This means that very narrow landmasses (such as the Isthmus of Panama) do not act as dispersal barriers in the simulations. As it is difficult to assess the validity of such barriers in deep time settings, this shortcoming is expected to produce random error in the provinciality calculations. Although the spatial extent of some provinces could not be reproduced exactly with the simulation (e.g. southern border of European province), they tend to differ in only some grid cells.

Sensitivity tests of free parameters

Higher dispersion thresholds (d) led to smaller average provinces (figure S1.7a-b). Although the volatility of the calculated provinciality series depended on the dispersion threshold, the patterns remained, the observed increase in the past 250 million years was significant in all simulation trials. The slope of the increase, however, is somewhat dependent on the minimum distance threshold (d) required for provinces to be separate as the continents drift apart.

PIE provinciality is insensitive to minimum province size (s_{min} , figure S1.7c), which only has minor time-inhomogeneous effects on provinciality itself. However, this parameter affects the number of produced provinces (figure S1.7d) more, especially in cases when the continents were more fragmented (due to the smaller expected size of the continents). The increasing detail of the reconstructed paleocoastlines and the complexity of the geographic distribution of shelf habitat [28] might also lead to more frequent small patches that this parameter is acting on (i.e. in the Cenozoic). The insensitivity of PIE provinciality to this parameter also demonstrates its robustness in the face of random sampling error that produces ‘noise modules’ in the biogeographic partitioning of occurrence data [24].

Geographic resolution's effect on simulation output

The geographic resolution of the simulations does not influence the calculation of PIE provinciality (figure S1.2). Although there is a systematic effect of the resolution change on the provinciality values, these do not affect the observed increase in the past 250 million years.

Observed biogeographies

Provinciality and the number of modules

Using fossil data, we identified 190 modules over the entire Phanerozoic (figure S1.8, supplementary item S3). Although PIE provinciality did not ($\rho = 0.15$, 95% CI: -0.10 – 0.38), the number of modules did increase over the Phanerozoic ($\rho = 0.39$, CI: 0.16 – 0.59), which is likely attributed to increase in fossil sampling. Both the spatiotemporal distribution and the number of provinces are affected by sampling biases. Sampling intensity, i.e. the number of sampled grid cells is correlated with the number of provinces per time interval ($\rho = 0.44$, CI: 0.25 – 0.59) and so is the median province latitude with median latitude of fossil occurrences ($\rho = 0.77$, CI: 0.69 – 0.84). The number of modules feature a similar increase over the last 250 million years as PIE provinciality (ρ with age = -0.78, -0.89 – -0.63). The number of Ordovician modules is as high as in the late Eocene (figures 2b, S1.8c),

Durations of provinces

Similar to taxon durations, province durations have right-skewed distributions. After the omission of extant provinces, the median duration of provinces in the raw partitioning output is decreases from 14.3 to 13.8 million years. This value increases to 25.5 million years, when single-interval provinces are also excluded. Further refining this result with the omission of range endpoints that are connected by unsampled stages suggests a median duration of 24.5 million years.

Early Palaeozoic (Cambrian-Silurian) provinces have significantly lower durations than younger provinces (19.5 vs. 25.9 million years, CI for median difference -0.8 – -13.2), which is even more prominent when extant provinces are included in the assessment (19.5 vs. 27.2 million years, CI for median difference -1.20 – -15.5). As biogeographic turnover is related to taxonomic turnover [23] this phenomenon is likely connected to the shorter durations of taxa in the Early Palaeozoic. The average durations of provinces tabulated for every stage reflect these patterns (figure S1.8d), although the values are considerable higher due to the temporal scatter of short-ranged provinces. The end-Permian mass extinction does not induce a significant difference in the average durations of the provinces.

Interpretation of biogeographic patterns

The validity of provinciality's temporal pattern depends on whether the approach can outline provinces that have a uniform definition, i.e. are comparable over time given the analyses parameters (geographic grid) and the characteristics of the dataset (number of occurrences, collections, sampled grid cells and time slices) - all of which translate to the parameters of partitioned network.

The quality of biogeographic partitionings changes over time, with some time-slices showing high spatial overlap between the network modules (e.g. mid-Cretaceous stages). Based on the apparent increase in the clarity of geographic render of the modules (provinces) as fossil sampling becomes more intensive in the Cenozoic, these random assignments can be attributed to sampling noise that manifests itself as random changes in biogeographic membership. This phenomenon suggests that higher spatial coverage and/or number of occurrences in a cell could eventually clarify even the noisy patterns.

Repeating the partitioning algorithm separately on the time bin-specific subsets of the data (figure S1.4a-b) suggests that neither the number of provinces, nor PIE provinciality of a time bin is sensitive to its context (i.e. the size of the network, the number of other time bins and their fauna). Results attained with this bin-specific partitioning of fossil occurrence data differ only slightly compared to when the entire network is partitioned. This suggests that the number of modules and PIE are comparable across the different time slices, and that the observed biogeographic partitionings

themselves are conditioned on 1) the biogeographic information itself, and 2) patterns of sampling in the time-bin. Thus, the meaningfulness of the patterns boils down to the question of how much the output patterns get distorted by sampling and the arbitrary parameters of the dataset.

Our earlier results with present-day occurrence data indicate that neither the number of occurrences nor spatial cells have a definitive effect on the clustering results, when random sampling is simulated with a subsampling protocol (Figure S1.8C in [24]). Highly incomplete sampling makes certain geographic cells represented by unique fauna that does not overlap with that of other areas of the globe. As noted previously by [19, 24], some modules produced by the partitioning approach and can be treated as ‘noise modules’ that arise due to sampling incompleteness and heterogeneity.

The projection of the original bipartite graph was suggested to conceal some modules [19, 24], and was also suggested to have the potential to obscure some coarse-level structure in the original graph [72]. However, it is also effective in reducing the number of ‘noise modules’ that arise when we partition a bipartite network that was created from fossil occurrence data (Figure S1.7 in [24]). The projection also makes the partitioning approach insensitive to cell size and within-cell sampling intensity (Figure S1.6 in [24]).

The resolution of the geographic grid deterministically constrains the minimum size of the provinces that can be outlined, therefore, changes in biogeographic structure that is on a finer scale than our chose geographic resolution cannot be detected with our approach. Our approach explicitly treats space and time as equally important in defining spatiotemporal modules, although this assumption can be relaxed with multilayer approaches [34]).

The ‘infomap’ console application produced almost identical results as the ‘igraph’ implementation. Changing the teleportation probability had no effect on our results. Forcing the partitioning algorithm to find smaller nodules with higher self-link teleportation (only with infomap 0.21.0, figure S1.9c) suggests that finer scale biogeographic structure might be present in the data (especially in the early Mesozoic), although it is not detectable either because of their small size, or their less pronounced connectivity patterns (i.e. distinctness in terms of faunal composition). Although increasing the self-link teleportation probability did produce smaller modules, these systematic changes do not affect our conclusions about the evolution of provinciality, that increases in the past 250 million years even with high a probability of 0.45 (ρ with age = -0.77, CI: -0.87 – -0.61).

The reduction of data necessary to run the analyses contribute to random sampling, and consequently also degrade the quality of the partitionings. Nevertheless, derived statistics seem to be robust, despite the changes of the geographic rendering of the partitionings. For the reasons above, we argue that the used methodology can provide an unbiased, yet imprecise tool to investigate past

marine biogeography.

Match of simulation and fossil data analysis results

Based on Adjusted Mutual Information (AMI) values (figure S1.10a), the simulated and observed partitionings match much better than completely random matches (AMI = 0; perfect match is indicated by 1). Results of the dynamic simulation match the observed biogeographic partitionings better than those based on the stable climate settings (*changingCC*), although not significantly (median AMI: 0.39 vs. 0.37 respectively, CI of difference in medians: -0.068 – 0.104). The relatively lower values are partially attributable to the low number of sampled cells (low geographic resolution necessary to analyse the fossil record) as well as the overall poor quality of the species-level fossil record. The match of observed with simulation partitionings declines with age ($\rho = -0.31$, CI: -0.12 – -0.51), possibly due to increasing uncertainties in both paleoenvironmental and fossil data. Values of provinciality (figure S1.10b) also share this declining match over time.

Mismatches are visually apparent on the geographic renders of the provinces as well (e.g. in figure 2). Although previous works on early Mesozoic benthic biogeography [20] suggest much more detailed structuring than our network partitioning approach, this conflict might arise due to our method's constant sensitivity over time to detect provinces. The low number of provinces in the Triassic-Early Jurassic interval can be the result of reduced biogeographic structure, perhaps due to the numerous evolutionary crises during this time [23]. Variation in the simulation free parameters (s_{min} and d_i) over time might also contribute to the declining match in the Mesozoic. This could have an evolutionary underpinning, i.e. temperature had a different determining effect on species' geographic ranges. However, based on the spatial overlap of some modules that the fossil data analysis produced, it is possible that the sampling patterns contribute more to the observed mismatches.

Partial simulation results

Repeating the simulation using the stable-climate scenario (*changingCC*, figure S1.6a), does not lead to an increasing pattern of provinciality ($\rho = -0.02$, CI: -0.39 – 0.35), suggesting that the changing latitudinal SST gradient is a key factor for the increasing provinciality. Keeping the present-day continental configuration stable, however (*changingT*) suggests a slight, long-term shift in the provinciality values (figure S1.6a), that can be interpreted as long-term increase (ρ with age = -0.68, CI: -0.39 – -0.87). The geographic patterns of fossil sampling (figure S1.6b) barely change this increase (ρ with age = -0.54, CI= -0.69 – -0.33).

Modelling provinciality

Fossil data

Linear models of provinciality based on mean SST and continent fragmentation suggest that both had significant (table S1.2) effects on provinciality. However, autocorrelation of the residuals of this regression were significant on the first lag, and the `forecast::auto.arima()` function suggested an autoregressive process to best fit the series ($ARI = 0.49$). Using this correlation structure in a GLS modelling of provinciality suggested that the slope of the parameters was no longer significant, and the observed association might be spurious.

Partial simulations

Linear modelling suggested that changes in the provinciality values in partial simulations matched changes of the provinciality values in the ‘dynamic’ simulation output (table S1.3). Although a moving average process was suggested for the residuals of the linear model with spatially complete simulation outputs ($MAI=0.57$, which was provided as correlation structure), the GLS method did not change the result that varying climate is a more important contributor to overall provinciality change.

Although, provinciality calculated from fossil data appears to be more determined by continental fragmentation than global mean SST, masking the spatially complete output of simulations to reproduce the incompleteness of fossil sampling reverses this pattern (table S1.3), so it matches the order of importance in the fossil record. The correlation structure for the GLS method was the same as with the spatially complete output (estimated $MAI = 0.46$).

Diversity and observed provinciality

Using the 95-bin timescale (table S3), the trajectory of subsampled genus richness is not correlated with the fossil data-based provinciality series over the whole Phanerozoic ($\rho = 0.19$, CI: $-0.027 - 0.403$). A strong correlation ($\rho = 0.63$, CI: $0.381 - 0.790$) was present only in the Mesozoic interval, where both series exhibit strong trends. The first differences of the two time series are not correlated, and the GLS-based analyses do not suggest that provinciality is a strong predictor of genus richness.

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Supplementary Figures and Tables

Figure S1.1. Scheme to demonstrate the problems with incomplete sampling and biogeographic structure. a. Complete spatial coverage, b. homogeneous random, c. heterogeneous sampling. Panels b and c represent the same sampling intensity (p_s). $|P|$ denotes the number of provinces. Black cells indicate unhabitable area.

Figure S1.2. The effect of geographic resolution on simulated provinciality. The simulation output was resampled to multiple geographic grids in every time slice before provinciality was recalculated. Although grid cell size has a systematic effect on provinciality these effects are minor and do not change the overall trajectory.

a

Partitioning output using OBIS benthic data
(Kocsis et al., 2018)

b

Dynamic simulation output with present-day
continent configuration and SST

Figure S1.3. Comparison of present-day biogeography of benthic taxa from OBIS to the dynamic simulation output using present day shelf distribution and SST. Free parameters of the simulation (dt and $smin$) were chosen to optimise the match between these two partitionings ($AMI = 0.83$). Besides the remarkable similarity of the two partitionings, the main differences include the lack of a boundary between Tropical West-Atlantic and Tropical East-Pacific due to the narrowness of the Isthmus of Panama; and the appearance of Temperate Southwest Atlantic province in the simulation output.

Figure S1.4. Comparison of the results of the biogeographic partitioning method obtained with the approach used throughout the manuscript (tracing) and when the partitioning method is applied separately to every time bin (slice-wise). a. The number of modules outlined in the partitioning. b. PIE calculated from the partitionings.

Figure S1.5. Genus-level Phanerozoic diversity curves from the subset of fossil data used in the partitioning analysis. Raw data (gray) are shown using the range-through (RT) diversity metric. Data used in the analyses (black) were standardised using the Shareholder Quorum Subsampling algorithm (quorum level of 0.6) and were counted with the corrected sampled-in-bin method (CSIB).

Figure S1.6. Simulation results varying continent configuration and temperature separately, while the other is held at the present-day state. Provinciality values calculated from partial simulations compared to the final (dynamic) simulation output based on a. complete geographic coverage and b. areas sampled in the fossil record. Continental configuration was kept stable in one partial run (Changing T, stable CC), while the other partial run featured stable mean temperatures (Changing CC, stable T). Long-term changes of provinciality are better described with temperature change.

Figure S1.7. Sensitivity tests for the free parameters of the simulation (d_t : a, b and s_{min} : c, d) , demonstrating their effect on provinciality (a, c) and the number of provinces (b, d). Provinciality is in general less sensitive than the number of provinces to the varying of the two parameters. Keeping small provinces in the simulation barely affects provinciality, suggesting robustness in light of ‘noise modules’ in the observed partitionings. All simulated trajectories show an increasing trend in the past 250 million years.

Figure S1.8. Phanerozoic marine provinces over time based on fossil occurrence data. a. The temporal distribution of provinces based on their median latitude across the time interval in which it appears. Thicker lines indicate that at least one sampled cell in a time slice is assigned to a province, thin lines represent interpolated ranges. b. Province sizes over the Phanerozoic. Colours represent different provinces and match those on figures 2b and in S3. c. The observed number of provinces through time. Note the trend in the past 250 million years. d. The mean duration of provinces ranging through every time slice. Single-interval provinces were excluded from the calculations. Provinces ranging to bin number 94 (Pleistocene) were treated as extant. Early Palaeozoic provinces have lower durations than the rest of the Phanerozoic. Note resemblance to work by Rojas et al. [34].

Figure S1.9. Comparison of results obtained using the infomap console application. a. The number of modules outlined in the partitioning in every time slice using the console application and ‘igraph’ implementation. b. PIE calculated from the partitioning using the console application and ‘igraph’ implementation. c. The effect of self-link teleportation on PIE provinciality.

Figure S1.10. Match between observed and simulated partitionings and derived provinciality values. a. AMI between partitionings derived from fossil data and simulation results. b. Error of provinciality in a bin is the absolute difference of the simulated and observed trajectories (solid line). Dashed line indicates the square root of the mean squared differences between the observed and simulated provinciality values in the part of the series that start from the time bin. The simulation model closely approximates observed values of provinciality over the last 170 million years. Mismatch between simulated and observed provinciality values is indicated for the Late Devonian and the Triassic-Early Jurassic interval.

Table S1.1. Timescales used in the study.

System	Stage	Bottom (Ma)	Mid (Ma)	Top (Ma)	Stage number (95-bin)	Assigned reconstruction	Reconstruction number (81-bin)
Ediacaran	Avalon Assemblage	575	567.5	560	1		
Ediacaran	White Sea Assemblage	560	554.5	549	2		
Ediacaran	Nama Assemblage	549	545	541	3		
Cambrian	Fortunian	541	535	529	4	535 Ma	1
Cambrian	Stage 2	529	525	521	5	525 Ma	2
Cambrian	Stage 3	521	517.5	514	6	515 Ma	3
Cambrian	Stage 4	514	511.5	509	7	510 Ma	4
Cambrian	Stage 5	509	506.75	504.5	8	505 Ma	5
Cambrian	Drumian	504.5	502.5	500.5	9	500 Ma	6
Cambrian	Guzhangian	500.5	498.75	497	10	500 Ma	6
Cambrian	Paibian	497	495.5	494	11	495 Ma	7
Cambrian	Jiangshanian	494	491.75	489.5	12	490 Ma	8
Cambrian	Lawsonian	489.5	487.45	485.4	13	485 Ma	9
Ordovician	Tremadocian	485.4	481.55	477.7	14	480 Ma	10
Ordovician	Floian	477.7	473.85	470	15	475 Ma	11
Ordovician	Dapingian	470	468.65	467.3	16	470 Ma	12
Ordovician	Darriwilian	467.3	462.85	458.4	17	465 Ma	13
Ordovician	Sandbian	458.4	455.7	453	18	455 Ma	14
Ordovician	Katian	453	449.1	445.2	19	450 Ma	15
Ordovician	Hirnantian	445.2	444.3	443.4	20	445 Ma	16
Silurian	Rhuddanian	443.4	442.1	440.8	21	440 Ma	17
Silurian	Aeronian	440.8	439.65	438.5	22	440 Ma	17
Silurian	Telychian	438.5	435.95	433.4	23	435 Ma	18
Silurian	Sheinwoodian	433.4	431.95	430.5	24	430 Ma	19
Silurian	Homerian	430.5	428.95	427.4	25	430 Ma	19
Silurian	Gorstian	427.4	426.5	425.6	26	425 Ma	20
Silurian	Ludfordian	425.6	424.3	423	27	425 Ma	20
Silurian	Pridoli	423	421.1	419.2	28	420 Ma	21
Devonian	Lochkovian	419.2	415	410.8	29	415 Ma	22
Devonian	Pragian	410.8	409.2	407.6	30	410 Ma	23
Devonian	Emsian	407.6	400.45	393.3	31	400 Ma	24
Devonian	Eifelian	393.3	390.5	387.7	32	390 Ma	25
Devonian	Givetian	387.7	385.2	382.7	33	385 Ma	26
Devonian	Frasnian	382.7	377.45	372.2	34	375 Ma	27
Devonian	Famennian	372.2	365.55	358.9	35	365 Ma	28
Carboniferous	Tournaisian	358.9	352.8	346.7	36	355 Ma	29
Carboniferous	Visean	346.7	338.8	330.9	37	340 Ma	30
Carboniferous	Serpukhovian	330.9	327.05	323.2	38	325 Ma	31
Carboniferous	Bashkirian	323.2	319.2	315.2	39	320 Ma	32
Carboniferous	Moscovian	315.2	311.1	307	40	310 Ma	33
Carboniferous	Kasimovian	307	305.35	303.7	41	305 Ma	34
Carboniferous	Gzhelian	303.7	301.3	298.9	42	300 Ma	35
Permian	Asselian	298.9	297.2	295.5	43	295 Ma	36
Permian	Sakmarian	295.5	292.8	290.1	44	295 Ma	36
Permian	Artinskian	290.1	284.7	279.3	45	285 Ma	37
Permian	Kungurian	279.3	275.8	272.3	46	275 Ma	38
Permian	Roadian	272.3	270.55	268.8	47	270 Ma	39

Permian	Wordian	268.8	266.95	265.1	48	265 Ma	40
Permian	Capitanian	265.1	262.5	259.9	49	260 Ma	41
Permian	Wuchiapingian	259.9	257.035	254.17	50	255 Ma	42
Permian	Changhsingian	254.17	253.17	252.17	51	255 Ma	42
Triassic	Induan	252.17	251.685	251.2	52	250 Ma	43
Triassic	Olenekian	251.2	249.2	247.2	53	250 Ma	43
Triassic	Anisian	247.2	244.6	242	54	245 Ma	44
Triassic	Ladinian	242	239.5	237	55	240 Ma	45
Triassic	Carnian	237	232.5	228	56	230 Ma	46
Triassic	Norian	228	218.25	208.5	57	220 Ma	47
Triassic	Rhaetian	208.5	204.9	201.3	58	205 Ma	48
Jurassic	Hettangian	201.3	200.3	199.3	59	200 Ma	49
Jurassic	Sinemurian	199.3	195.05	190.8	60	195 Ma	50
Jurassic	Pliensbachian	190.8	186.75	182.7	61	185 Ma	51
Jurassic	Toarcian	182.7	178.4	174.1	62	180 Ma	52
Jurassic	Aalenian	174.1	172.2	170.3	63	170 Ma	53
Jurassic	Bajocian	170.3	169.3	168.3	64	170 Ma	53
Jurassic	Bathonian	168.3	167.2	166.1	65	165 Ma	54
Jurassic	Callovian	166.1	164.8	163.5	66	165 Ma	54
Jurassic	Oxfordian	163.5	160.4	157.3	67	160 Ma	55
Jurassic	Kimmeridgian	157.3	154.7	152.1	68	155 Ma	56
Jurassic	Tithonian	152.1	148.55	145	69	150 Ma	57
Cretaceous	Berriasian	145	142.4	139.8	70	140 Ma	58
Cretaceous	Valanginian	139.8	136.35	132.9	71	135 Ma	59
Cretaceous	Hauterivian	132.9	131.15	129.4	72	130 Ma	60
Cretaceous	Barremian	129.4	127.2	125	73	125 Ma	61
Cretaceous	Aptian	125	119	113	74	120 Ma	62
Cretaceous	Albian	113	106.75	100.5	75	105 Ma	63
Cretaceous	Cenomanian	100.5	97.2	93.9	76	95 Ma	64
Cretaceous	Turonian	93.9	91.85	89.8	77	90 Ma	65
Cretaceous	Coniacian	89.8	88.05	86.3	78	90 Ma	65
Cretaceous	Santonian	86.3	84.95	83.6	79	85 Ma	66
Cretaceous	Campanian	83.6	77.85	72.1	80	80 Ma	67
Cretaceous	Maastrichtian	72.1	69.05	66	81	70 Ma	68
Paleogene	Danian	66	63.8	61.6	82	65 Ma	69
Paleogene	Selandian-Thanetian	61.6	58.8	56	83	60 Ma	70
Paleogene	Ypresian	56	51.9	47.8	84	50 Ma	71
Paleogene	Lutetian	47.8	44.55	41.3	85	45 Ma	72
Paleogene	Bartonian	41.3	39.65	38	86	40 Ma	73
Paleogene	Priabonian	38	35.95	33.9	87	35 Ma	74
Paleogene	Rupelian	33.9	31	28.1	88	30 Ma	75
Paleogene	Chattian	28.1	25.565	23.03	89	25 Ma	76
Neogene	Lower Miocene	23.03	19.5	15.97	90	20 Ma	77
Neogene	Middle Miocene	15.97	13.795	11.62	91	15 Ma	78
Neogene	Upper Miocene	11.62	8.4765	5.333	92	10 Ma	79
Neogene	Pliocene	5.333	3.9605	2.588	93	5 Ma	80
Quaternary	Pleistocene	2.588	1.29985	0.0117	94	0 Ma	81
Quaternary	Holocene	0.0117	0.00585	0	95	0 Ma	81

Table S1.2. Modelling provinciality from fossil data analysis.

	parameter	Value	Std.Error	<i>t</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value
OLS	(Intercept)	-0.03	0.1012	-0.3445	0.73146
	shelfarea	-0.21	0.1084	-1.8923	0.06231
	sst	-0.19	0.1039	-1.8374	0.07011
	contfrag	0.49	0.1104	4.4334	<0.0001
	sst:contfrag	0.17	0.0907	1.8308	0.0711
OLS (first differences)	(Intercept)	0.01	0.0964	0.1402	0.88891
	shelfarea	0.03	0.1696	0.1651	0.86935
	sst	0.03	0.1536	0.1838	0.85464
	contfrag	-0.09	0.2553	-0.3695	0.71282
	sst:contfrag	0.16	0.53	0.3027	0.76294
GLS	(Intercept)	-0.04	0.2187	-0.1733	0.86288
	shelfarea	-0.04	0.1487	-0.2715	0.78679
	sst	-0.05	0.1374	-0.3931	0.69535
	contfrag	0.24	0.1773	1.3461	0.18232
	sst:contfrag	0.11	0.0981	1.1236	0.26478

Table S1.3. Modelling provinciality of the ‘dynamic’ simulation output.

	parameter	Value	Std.Error	<i>t</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value
Spatially complete, OLS	(Intercept)	-1.26	0.3385	-3.726	0.00037
	ccChange	0.73	0.1455	5.0183	< 0.0001
	sstChange	1.85	0.3582	5.1583	< 0.0001
Spatially complete, OLS (first differences)	(Intercept)	0	0.0071	0.001	0.99921
	ccChange	0.49	0.2066	2.3739	0.0201
	sstChange	0.7	0.4954	1.4066	0.16358
Spatially complete, GLS	(Intercept)	-0.82	0.3597	-2.2817	0.02523
	ccChange	0.62	0.1648	3.734	0.00036
	sstChange	1.39	0.3844	3.6267	0.00051
Sampled area, OLS	parameter	Value	Std.Error	<i>t</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value
	(Intercept)	-0.01	0.0443	-0.3294	0.74261
	ccChange	0.59	0.0714	8.2882	< 0.0001
Sampled area, OLS (first differences)	sstChange	0.33	0.0752	4.3732	< 0.0001
	(Intercept)	0	0.0122	0.0698	0.94454
	ccChange	0.64	0.0996	6.3979	< 0.0001
Sampled area, GLS	sstChange	0.24	0.0813	3.0032	0.00345
	(Intercept)	0	0.0484	-0.0199	0.98418
	ccChange	0.6	0.0803	7.4952	< 0.0001
	sstChange	0.3	0.0726	4.127	< 0.0001

Additional supplementary items

- S2. Biogeographic partitionings produced with the main ('dynamic') simulation framework using the 81-bin time scale (table S1.1).
- S3. Biogeographic partitionings in stages of the 95-bin time scale (table S1.1) of the Phanerozoic based on fossil data analysis. Colours match those of figures 2b and S1.8.
- S4. Original bipartite network and its unipartite projection that we used in the clustering approach.
- S5. Data plotted on figure 3.
- S6. Interpolated temperature reconstructions based on the HadCM3L climate models and the PaleoMAP Paleocoastlines.

Used data, code and the rest of the supplementary items are available on Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3973037>.